

Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI): Policy on Biorisk Assessment and Biosecurity Measures

(MIRRI-ERIC Policies)

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Executive Summary

Microbial domain biological resource centres (mBRC) provide live cultures, their associated data and expertise to foster and support the development of basic and applied science. Based on a long tradition, individual not-for-profit mBRCs were established to add value to known and yet unknown microbial biodiversity and to exploit unknown sources and knowledge to discover and disclose for the bioeconomy and bioscience. For several decades, collaboration among some mBRCs resulted in the achievement of several common goals of mutual interest. The pan-European Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI) has been established to go beyond these first hesitant collaborating attempts.

Directed by the MIRRI mission and user needs the current independent, often institutional policies and managed processes will be adapted by partner mBRCs to harmonize holdings, services, the training offer, accession policy and share expertise.

Better managed resources provided with legal compliance coupled with improved interaction with stakeholders will lead to further discovery in all areas of the Life Sciences. Therefore, a vision of knowledge transfer has been outlined to offer access to human expertise, to increase knowledge and promote professional development, and to provide a platform for long-term sustainability of microbial biodiversity. The knowledge transfer will be realized through a virtual Collaborative Working Environment inspiring excellence and to drive collaboration across borders and disciplines.

The following pages include the Policy on Biorisk Assessment and Biosecurity Measures of the Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure MIRRI, a prerequisite for public mBRCs to join MIRRI as partners in the envisaged legal entity MIRRI-ERIC as indicated in the Partner Charter.

For more information on MIRRI please visit our website www.mirri.org.

MIRRI Policy on Biorisk Assessment and Biosecurity Measures

Effective Biosecurity risk management is more than reliable and appropriate risk assessment. It also involves assigning responsibilities to members of staff and communication to (internal) staff and third parties (users). In this context awareness raising is the most fundamental basis for implementation of biosecurity and requires educational programs in the future in order to communicate broadly what biosecurity is and why biosecurity measures are demanded. MIRRI's policy will capture this and also addresses the issue in its training and education offer.

The key elements of the MIRRI policy on biorisk management in mBRCs

1. Follow the relevant national law
 - a. adhere to the Code of Conduct on Biosecurity for BRCs¹
 - b. other comparable recognized standards
 - c. OECD Best Practice Guidelines on Biosecurity for BRCs;
2. Follow the development of biosecurity implementation strategies and adjust practice accordingly;
3. Work in collaboration with MIRRI- and external partners towards developing and implementing protocols for adequate biosecurity risk assessment of holdings and normative compliance in MIRRI-mBRCs;
4. Offer available specific expertise to the MIRRI biosecurity expert cluster;
5. Work with national authorities to increase competence and advocate the establishment of national biosecurity offices and their international cooperation;
6. Work in collaboration with MIRRI- and external partners to strengthen the ethical basis for biosecurity in the scientific community;
7. Adopt existing or develop new educational tools to raise awareness among mBRC staff.

¹ Christine Rohde, David Smith, Dunja Martin, Dagmar Fritze, and Joost Stalpers (2013). Code of Conduct on Biosecurity for Biological Resource Centres: procedural implementation. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology* 63, 2374-2382. http://ijs.sgmjournals.org/content/63/Pt_7/2374.long